

Timeline of Resurrection of all Mankind

Written below is the approximate timeline of the resurrection of all the people who have ever lived. A process spanning from the year 2264 till the 63rd millennium with a total of 106 billion people resurrected.

Period of time	Total of People Resurrected
2264 (Year)	1
24 th Century	10
25 th Century	30
26 th Century	70
27 th Century	1K
3 rd Millennium	3K
4 th Millennium	5K
5 th Millennium	9K
7 th Millennium	13K
9 th Millennium	25K
10 th Millennium	37K
12 th Millennium	52K
14 th Millennium	120K
15 th Millennium	250K
17 th Millennium	500K
20 th Millennium	1M
22 nd Millennium	3M
23 rd Millennium	5M
24 th Millennium	8M
26 th Millennium	19M
28 th Millennium	35M
30 th Millennium	72M
32 nd Millennium	120M
35 th Millennium	260M
40 th Millennium	520M
43 rd Millennium	1.2B
45 th Millennium	1.7B
47 th Millennium	3.2B
50 th Millennium	6.5B
52 nd Millennium	13B
55 th Millennium	25B
58 th Millennium	56B

60 th Millennium	75B
63 rd Millennium	106B